

Exploring the Drivers of Tourist Purchasing Decisions at Pop-Up Fashion Retail Outlets in Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the key factors influencing tourists' shopping behavior in fashion pop-up stores in Saudi Arabia, which have emerged as a modern retail phenomenon playing an increasingly significant role in diversifying economic and tourism activities. A quantitative research approach was employed, utilizing a structured questionnaire to collect data from 304 participants in Riyadh and Jeddah during the peak tourism seasons. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple regression analysis to test the proposed hypotheses.

The findings revealed that the store environment was the most influential factor shaping tourists' purchasing decisions, followed by ephemerality, which created a sense of urgency among consumers, and product novelty and uniqueness, which strongly motivated purchases of exclusive designs. Shopping enjoyment, although less influential, was found to enhance the overall consumer experience. The study concluded that pop-up stores should focus on improving store atmospherics, emphasizing product scarcity, and offering innovative and unique designs.

Practical recommendations include integrating aesthetic and entertainment elements into pop-up stores—such as colors, music, and promotional events—to create a more enjoyable shopping experience and enhance store attractiveness. The study also suggests future research directions, such as comparing consumer behavior between permanent and temporary stores, examining the role of cultural and social factors, and exploring the impact of digital marketing on consumer engagement with pop-up retail.

Keywords: Pop-up fashion stores, tourist behavior, store environment, ephemerality, product novelty, shopping enjoyment.

1.1 Introduction

One of the most effective strategies used by marketers to sell their products is the use of Pop-Up Stores, which are temporary retail spaces typically employed to introduce a new product line, test a new market, or generate awareness of a product, service, or brand (Coupey, 2014). A temporary branch store is typically established in high-traffic areas, such as busy streets, shopping malls, and city centers (Haas & Schmidt, 2014). Researchers have coined the term “flash retailing” to describe pop-up stores, as this concept combines the flexibility of online retail with the increased consumer engagement offered by traditional face-to-face sales (Anja, 2014; Picot-Coupey, 2017). It is worth noting that major global retailers such as Amazon, CHANEL, Dior, Fila, and Macy's have adopted this approach to promote their brands.

Many stores have therefore sought to develop their businesses to reach consumers more quickly by observing and monitoring their purchasing behavior. This aims to increase the level of supply and demand for their products, boost sales and market share, strengthen competitive capabilities, and ultimately increase trust in the brand (Chris et al., 2009).

A review of previous studies (Boustani, 2021; Kim & Jeong, 2010; Padmalia, 2014) conducted to examine consumer behavior and its impact toward pop-up stores revealed mixed results, with both positive and negative consumer perceptions. Some researchers found that consumers perceive shopping from pop-up stores as risky, believing they will be unable to exchange or return their purchases once the store disappears. Zogaj et al. (2019) demonstrated the significant impact of pop-up retailing on consumer reactions to both products and brands. Ryu (2011) further highlighted consumer behavior and purchase intentions within pop-up stores, noting that such insights help develop effective pop-up retailing strategies to reach consumers better.

Padmalia (2018) noted that both internal and external factors of pop-up stores—such as location, interior design, and exterior design—have a direct impact on consumer behavior. This finding was supported by Thomas et al. (2018) and Alexander et al. (2018). Previous studies primarily focused on comparing consumer behavior in traditional shopping versus pop-up stores or examined pop-up stores as an independent subject. However, they did not specifically investigate the impact of fashion pop-up retailing on consumer behavior and shopping intentions. Ryu (2011) confirmed this gap through his study, which examined consumer behavior and marketing intentions in fashion pop-up stores.

The results of previous studies on consumer behavior toward pop-up stores indicate that demographic factors, beliefs, and other variables influence consumers' behavior and purchase intentions (Ryu, 2011; Alexander et al., 2018; Coupey, 2014; Niehm et al., 2007; Boustani, 2021; Kim & Jeong, 2010; Padmalia, 2014; Henkel & Toporowski, 2022; Zogaj et al., 2019; Roberts & Simpson, 2020; Chris et al., 2009; Kim, 2003; Lucy, 2010).

It is worth noting that Saudi Arabia has recently gained recognition for its major festivals and seasonal events, which are held annually in various parts of the Kingdom (Saudi Commission for Tourism and National Heritage, 2015). These events attract large numbers of both citizens and tourists. These events are organized in a manner that highlights Saudi heritage and culture (Saudi Ministry of Information, 2022). With the emergence of “Saudi Seasons” and the revitalization of tourism in the Kingdom, the phenomenon of pop-up stores has spread across various seasons, including fashion pop-up stores.

By reviewing recent studies and developments, it becomes clear that Saudi Arabia is making extensive efforts to develop the tourism sector as a key economic driver and one of the main pillars of Vision 2030. The goal is to diversify and strengthen the Saudi economy, attract investments, increase income, and create job opportunities. The Kingdom aims to raise tourism’s contribution to GDP to 10% and achieve 100 million visits by 2030, positioning Saudi Arabia among the world’s top five tourist destinations. Consequently, Saudi Arabia has topped the list of the most tourist-attractive Arab countries through several initiatives and innovative tourism programs, including the establishment of bazaars, seasonal markets, entertainment cities, the development of islands and tourist destinations, and the encouragement of private-sector investment in tourism (Saudi Entertainment Authority, 2022).

Accordingly, this study aims to identify the factors influencing tourist behavior in Saudi Arabia toward shopping at fashion pop-up stores.

1.2 Problem of the Study

The problem addressed in this study revolves around understanding tourists’ purchasing behavior and the factors that influence it. Given that this research focuses specifically on tourist behavior in fashion pop-up stores, it is essential to highlight the importance of tourism. Tourism has received significant attention at both international and regional levels due to its impact on social structures, development, and its direct influence on a country’s economy (Henkel & Toporowski, 2021).

Therefore, studying tourist consumer behavior is crucial because it is closely tied to the future of the tourism industry in any country. Maintaining a strong national brand and tourism reputation, as well as ensuring the continued flow of tourists to destinations, depends on understanding and responding to tourists’ purchasing behaviors. Host countries, therefore, pay special attention to tourists’ shopping behavior and provide incentives and attractions to encourage spending (Duong & Khuong, 2019).

This study stems from the importance of examining consumer behavior in general and tourist purchasing behavior in particular, which motivated the researcher to conduct this study. It focuses on tourist shopping behavior in Saudi Arabia by exploring the factors that influence shopping at fashion pop-up stores.

As mentioned earlier, Saudi Arabia is now well known for its major annual festivals and seasons held across various regions (Saudi Commission for Tourism and National

Heritage, 2015), which draw both citizens and tourists. However, most previous studies have focused on the impact of pop-up stores in terms of brand marketing and consumer attitudes toward the brand itself, without exploring tourist consumer behavior in the host country.

The present study, therefore, focuses on tourists' behavior toward pop-up stores in Saudi Arabia, aiming to identify the factors that influence tourists' shopping behavior in temporary fashion pop-up stores located in Saudi tourist areas.

The problem of the study can be summarized through the following questions:

1.3 Research Questions

Main Question:

What are the factors influencing tourist behavior toward shopping at fashion pop-up stores in Saudi Arabia?

1.4 Research Objectives

The primary objective of this study is to identify the factors influencing tourist consumer behavior toward shopping at fashion pop-up stores in tourist areas of Saudi Arabia.

1.5 Significance of the Study

The importance of this study lies in its contribution to highlighting tourist behavior toward shopping at pop-up stores, which represents one of the most critical issues directly affecting the purchasing and sales policies of any store. It is also considered one of the key strategic decisions faced by top management.

The present study contributes to enriching theoretical literature and academic resources related to consumer behavior research in general, tourist consumer behavior, shopping intentions, and purchase behavior in particular, with a focus on fashion pop-up stores.

The study focuses on pop-up stores at festivals and seasonal events held in Saudi Arabia, examining their role in boosting clothing sales and purchases. Moreover, the study is expected to yield findings that may contribute to building brand trust and enhancing consumers' purchase intentions in the fashion retail sector.

This study provides recommendations that may help improve marketing strategies for the Ministry of Commerce and Tourism, business owners, and retail investors. These recommendations aim to deepen their understanding of tourist behavior and strengthen tourists' purchase intentions toward specific brands.

The study also contributes to promoting tourism, which has become one of the most important areas for achieving Saudi Vision 2030.

2.1 Section One: Theoretical Framework

This chapter presents a literature review of previous studies related to the topic, aiming to clarify the concepts of consumer behavior, its importance, and the factors that

influence purchasing decisions. It also examines the concept of fashion pop-up stores from various perspectives, including the factors that influence tourist behavior toward them. Additionally, it enriches the literature by addressing the impact of the internal environment of fashion pop-up stores, product novelty and uniqueness, and the perishability effect on tourist behavior in Saudi Arabia.

2.1.1 Concept of Consumer Behavior

Studying consumer behavior is a fundamental step toward understanding consumers' purchasing nature and intentions, as well as the surrounding conditions that influence their purchasing decisions. Consumers' shopping behavior is shaped by the benefits and concerns that influence their decision to adopt specific shopping practices. Most consumer decisions are influenced by trust, which is considered a major barrier to making purchase decisions (Saeed & Badar, 2021).

For retailers and pop-up stores, understanding the managerial implications of stimulating shopping behavior is one of the most effective ways to gain deeper insight into consumer behavior. This includes improving service quality by leveraging factors that influence consumers, offering a wide variety of products, facilitating payment, focusing on product quality, providing competitive prices, offering detailed product information, and enhancing data privacy and security. All of these contribute to achieving the desired benefits and minimizing risks and concerns that affect consumer purchasing decisions—such as the risk of perishability (Zogaj et al., 2019; Thomas et al.).

Studies have shown that the concept of consumer behavior refers to the direct actions and behaviors of consumers in obtaining the products or services they desire and making purchasing decisions accordingly. Research has shown a clear difference between ordinary consumers and tourist consumers in the way they engage in the buying and selling process, which typically occurs over a shorter time period for tourists compared to ordinary consumers. However, this does not prevent ordinary consumers from behaving like tourist consumers when searching for the product attributes they want in a pop-up store.

Zhang (2015) explained that consumer behavior represents the final stage in a series of processes within the consumer, including needs, perception, motivation, desires, and intelligence. Hosany and Martin (2012) defined consumer behavior as the actions and behaviors individuals take when planning to acquire products for purchase and consumption. Others describe it as the set of actions taken by consumers when searching for, purchasing, and using goods and services.

Kotler (1973) described consumer behavior as a series of direct actions taken by individuals to obtain a product or service, including deciding to purchase. Other studies defined consumer behavior as the behavior displayed while searching for or using goods, services, ideas, or experiences, based on consumers' purchasing power, in order to satisfy a specific need. It also encompasses a set of mental and physical actions involved in purchasing and using products and services, as well as evaluating and comparing them (Happ et al., 2020).

Taube and Warnaby (2017) noted that consumer behavior is also a form of economic behavior, based on research and management, that aims to maximize benefits while fulfilling personal goals. When consumers search for goods and services, purchase them, use them, and evaluate them, they are essentially acting to meet their needs, desires, and motivations (Zogaj et al., 2019).

From the above, a derived definition of consumer behavior can be formulated: it is a set of rational actions and behaviors that stem from the individual's will as a consumer. This behavior is expressed through purchasing and using a product to satisfy needs and desires, or choosing not to purchase, following a purchase decision process that ends in either acceptance or rejection based on consumer conviction.

The researchers view consumer behavior as the actions taken by consumers when using or purchasing products, services, ideas, or experiences that they expect will meet their needs or desires within their purchasing capabilities, as well as the decisions made beforehand and their influence on these behaviors.

2.1.2 Importance of Consumer Behavior

Consumers today prefer simpler ways to access brands and stores. Pop-up stores have transformed consumer perceptions of convenience, speed, pricing, and product/service information, creating new ways to deliver value to customers, build relationships, and provide security, information, shipping, quality, pricing, and time efficiency. These factors positively affect customer satisfaction and willingness to shop (Kotler, 1973).

The importance of studying consumer behavior lies in its benefits to all parties involved in the exchange process—consumers, industrial and commercial institutions, marketers, and others. It provides essential knowledge and facts that help consumers make informed decisions aligned with their needs, preferences, purchasing power, and financial resources (Hosany & Martin, 2012).

It also helps consumers gain insight into the process of purchasing and using products and services, particularly regarding what they buy, why they buy it, and how they obtain it. Additionally, it allows them to understand the reasons and influences shaping their consumption and purchasing decisions, guiding them toward choosing specific products, brands, or services (Noth, 1988).

For industrial and commercial institutions, major organizations rely on consumer behavior research—especially primary research they conduct or utilize—to plan what to produce in terms of quantity and quality, in order to satisfy the needs of current and potential customers, based on their abilities, preferences, and motivations.

On one hand, it helps organizations select the optimal marketing mix for their products or services. On the other hand, it increases the likelihood of identifying potential marketing opportunities. When it comes to spending priorities and the allocation of financial resources, industrial and commercial institutions—such as producers and marketers—can benefit from primary consumer behavior research to inform their

manufacturing and marketing strategies for products (Taube & Warnaby, 2017; Zhang, 2015; Hosany & Martin, 2012).

The study of tourist consumer behavior also assists owners of both temporary and permanent stores in designing appropriate marketing strategies. It helps them understand why and when tourists make purchasing decisions. Moreover, it enables them to identify marketing opportunities amidst intense competition, allowing businesses to capitalize on unmet market needs. Additionally, responding quickly to changes in consumer needs and desires, along with the continuous development and improvement of tourism services, is essential. Every tourism enterprise must strive to offer products that meet the needs and preferences of consumers (López-Sanz et al., 2021).

Analyzing tourist consumer behavior is crucial for both temporary and permanent store owners, as it enables them to develop effective marketing plans. Furthermore, it helps them understand how and when tourists make decisions, enabling them to discover new marketing opportunities. Businesses can capitalize on unmet marketing needs, even in the face of fierce competition. Therefore, every tourism organization must aim to deliver products that meet the requirements and desires of both regular consumers and tourists, while taking into account the distinct needs of each group. It should also design and enhance tourism services, responding swiftly to shifts in consumer demands and preferences (Halkiopoulos et al., 2022).

Based on this, the researcher believes that studying tourist consumer behavior benefits all parties involved in the marketing process—from individual consumers to families as consumption units, and from organizations to industrial and commercial enterprises. To fully understand the factors influencing consumer behavior, store management must examine consumer attitudes and behavior, as well as how consumers react to future manufacturer policies.

2.1.3 Types of Consumer Behavior

Different types of consumers can be described based on their behavior, each with distinctive characteristics. Schiffman et al. (2013) identified four main categories of consumers: individual, industrial, intermediary, and final consumers. They can be outlined as follows:

1. Final Consumer: Purchases goods and services for personal or family use.
2. Industrial Consumer: Refers collectively to both public and private institutions. These entities purchase products, supplies, or machinery to achieve their strategic objectives. They also buy components—either fully or semi-finished—to produce and sell finished goods to final or industrial consumers.
3. Intermediary Consumer: May be represented by individuals or organizations that primarily buy and resell goods for profit. At this level, consumers often purchase in bulk, relying on complete information about the products and services.

From the above, we can conclude that there are three main types of consumers:

- The final consumer, who purchases goods and services for end use.
- The industrial consumer, who buys raw materials to produce other goods.
- The intermediary consumer, such as wholesalers and retailers, who purchase goods for resale (Gronholdt et al., 2000).

Additionally, consumer behavior is shaped by four key factors:

- Whether the behavior is overt or covert.
- Whether it is innate or acquired.
- The frequency of behaviors, either individual or collective.
- The degree of novelty or repetition in the behavior.

These factors are used to classify consumer behavior as new, repetitive, or significantly altered (Bird et al., 1970; Schiffman et al., 2013).

The researcher argues that consumer behavior largely depends on two main categories of consumers: the final consumer, who regularly purchases goods and services for their own use or that of their family; and the industrial consumer, who buys resources or goods to aid in production or service delivery. The decision-making process of the latter tends to be more complex, involving multiple alternatives. From the perspective of motivation and consumption, tourist consumers do not differ from regular consumers in their basic purchasing behavior. However, there are differences in the type of consumption and method of purchase.

Moreover, tourist behavior is not purely individual; the interaction between the individual and the group influences behavioral differences. Cultural and economic factors also shape general behavior patterns and, more specifically, tourist behavior. Additionally, people's actions are not expressed spontaneously; they are formed within structured frameworks that govern them.

2.1.4 Factors Affecting the Consumer's Purchasing Decision

One of the most important consumer activities is the purchasing decision-making process, which aims to satisfy consumer desires and needs. This stage involves purchasing the product and testing it. Since both internal and external factors influence individual consumers, the purchasing decision-making process involves multiple steps, making it a more complex and challenging process. Consumers continually strive to meet their needs and allocate their limited resources to goods and services that best fulfill their evolving demands.

The purchasing decision is defined as the culmination of a mental process that leads to a fair and reasonable price, balanced consumer spending, and the optimal fulfillment of needs (Fornell, 1992). It also refers to the stages and processes customers go through when determining which products they wish to buy. It can be described as the deliberate

selection of one option from two or more alternatives in situations that require thoughtful study and effort to achieve, such as integrating a new activity into a business, changing a company's strategy, or determining how to achieve corporate goals (Happ et al., 2020).

Others have defined it as “the desire to obtain a specific benefit, modified by a set of constraints surrounding the individual, such as the available market elements and the influence of marketing policies.” It has also been described as a set of deliberations that precede and guide the acquisition, use, and consumption of goods and services (Kotler et al., 1973). These factors represent a repetitive, diverse, and sequential process of selecting a product or service, ranging from simple, routine decisions to those that require significant time, effort, and money.

The **five roles** played by the final consumer during the purchasing decision process are as follows:

1. **Initiator:** The person who proposes or first suggests the idea of purchasing a specific product or brand. Depending on the nature of the product (e.g., a car, washing machine, or specific clothing), this may be the husband, wife, or children (Saeed & Badar, 2021).
2. **Influencer:** The person or group who influences someone to make a purchasing decision. They possess knowledge, persuasive skills, and the ability to communicate and promote their point of view to others. Family members, friends, or colleagues may act as influencers (Arpita & Subhro, 2021).
3. **Purchasing Decision Maker:** The individual who has the authority to make the purchasing decision. Decision-makers differ depending on the product's value, cost, and intended use. Within a family, for example, some products—such as food and children's clothing—are decided upon by the homemaker. In contrast, other products may only be purchased by the head of the household (Bae & Jeon, 2022).
4. **Buyer:** The person who physically makes the purchase, regardless of whether they participated in the decision-making process. Their role is limited to executing the transaction. The buyer may or may not be one of the end users (Happ et al., 2020).
5. **User:** The individual who ultimately uses or consumes the product or service. Users may influence product demand and selection, or they may not (Taube & Warnaby, 2017).

From the above definitions, we can conclude that the process of selecting products to fulfill consumer desires is complex, involving multiple stages and roles: the initiator, the influencer, the decision-maker, the buyer, and the user.

By linking regular consumer behavior with tourist consumer behavior, we find that behavior itself is based on benefits and concerns that influence their decision to engage

in shopping. Most consumer decisions are influenced by the trust factor, which is a significant barrier preventing consumers from making informed purchasing decisions.

Given the research gap addressed in this study, the implications of tourist behavior for retailers and temporary stores are significant. Encouraging and motivating tourists to shop is one of the most effective ways to gain a deeper understanding of their behavior and preferences. This, in turn, leads to improved service quality by using factors that influence them, offering a wide range of products, simplifying payment procedures, and ensuring the quality of the goods offered (Alshawagfih et al., 2015).

Moreover, understanding the variables that influence tourist behavior enables retailers to offer competitive prices, provide clear product information, and enhance levels of data security and privacy for tourists. This helps achieve the desired benefits while avoiding risks and concerns that influence tourist purchasing decisions, such as the risk of disappearance or product unavailability (Zdon-Korzeniowska, 2019).

The researcher argues that many factors influence consumer purchasing decisions. These may be internal factors related to the consumer's personal needs for goods and services, or product-specific factors tied to the characteristics of the item they wish to purchase. There are also external factors related to the consumer's environment and the producer, such as economic, cultural, and political factors. To meet the diverse needs of consumers and facilitate the purchasing process, service providers and business owners focus on identifying consumers and analyzing their behavior.

2.1.5 Stages of the Consumer's Purchasing Decision-Making Process

When consumers choose the goods and services they wish to purchase, they typically go through several essential steps in the decision-making process. These steps can be summarized in five main stages:

1. Realizing the Problem and Identifying the Need:

This is the **first stage** in the consumer's purchasing decision. It varies from one person to another depending on individual needs and desires, as well as supply and demand on the seller's side. For example, one consumer may view purchasing a certain product as essential because it represents the best way to improve performance and meet internal and external needs. Another consumer may view the same product as non-essential or simply an additional luxury (Hosany & Martin, 2012).

This variation in consumer needs and desires ultimately benefits marketers and retailers. Their role here is to participate in promotional activities, typically through media, to increase consumer awareness of the available products, their features, advantages, and benefits according to each consumer's needs. This helps buyers solve their problems in line with the product's characteristics (Zhang, 2015).

2. Finding Information:

The second stage begins once the consumer identifies a problem and starts seeking information. This involves **internal search**, where the consumer relies on memory of various brands and alternative products that can meet their needs. It also involves **external search**, which becomes more important when the cost of the product is high or when demand is expected to increase significantly, either partially or entirely (Kotler, 1973).

The main sources of external information include:

- **Personal factors:** family and friends.
- **Public factors:** media, consumer protection associations, government bodies.
- **Commercial factors:** advertising, salespeople, point-of-purchase displays, etc.

Here, the consumer receives relevant information through advertisements, personal interaction with sales representatives, or direct messages, all of which influence their purchase decision.

3. Evaluation of Alternatives:

At this stage, consumers now have a **wide range of options** to meet their needs. Due to advancements and competition in the market, many alternatives become available. For instance, when buying higher-value goods such as clothing or shoes, consumers are faced with multiple choices (Taube & Warnaby, 2017).

Evaluating these alternatives is one of the most critical steps in the purchasing process. Consumers must examine and compare the available options before making a decision. They may visit multiple stores to make an informed choice. When consumers make a purchase, they aim to choose the best option from their perspective and avoid potential losses (Happ et al., 2020).

The researcher notes that the consumer decision-making process generally follows these stages:

- A problem or need arises, motivating the consumer to begin the purchasing process.
- This is followed by information search about the product or service.
- Next comes the evaluation of alternatives, where the consumer assesses their options based on the information collected.
- Once the best product or service is identified, the consumer is ready to make the purchase decision.

Marketers must place themselves in the consumer's position and think through these steps to effectively sell products.

2.1.8 Factors Influencing Tourist Behavior to Shop from Pop-Up Fashion Stores

Consumers are exposed to a range of factors that influence their behavior and shape their purchasing patterns for goods and services. These factors shape consumers' purchasing decisions, particularly in the context of pop-up stores, and stem from both internal factors within the individual and external environmental factors related to the store itself.

During the evaluation stage and before making a purchasing decision, consumers classify brands and form their purchase intentions, ultimately deciding to buy the brand that they perceive as the best among the available alternatives (Turley & Milliman, 2000).

Research indicates that consumer perceptions of pop-up stores differ from their perceptions of traditional brick-and-mortar stores. Ibrahim and Chua (2010) investigated consumer perceptions of temporary and permanent retail spaces in shopping malls and found that consumers associate pop-up stores with three main dimensions:

- **Store design,**
- **Layout,** and
- **Product display.**

These elements reflect the variety of products offered and the brand's service quality. Consumers also perceive pop-up stores as more accessible than traditional stores, suggesting a preference for them in some cases.

Studies have shown that the store's internal environment has a direct effect on shopping behavior. Since the 1970s, Kotler (1973) has noted that the controlled in-store environment can influence customers' emotional states, increasing the likelihood of purchase.

More recent research has examined how specific environmental cues—such as music, lighting, color, and striking arrangements—affect consumer emotional responses, evaluations of products/retailers, shopping satisfaction, and purchase intentions (Henkel & Toporowski, 2021).

The internal environment of a store is under the retailer's control, though it is typically not changed frequently unless redesign projects are implemented periodically (e.g., annually or semi-annually). Given the competitive nature of pop-up stores, their lifespan often depends on periodic redesign (Ryu, 2011).

Generally, retailers focus on internal factors such as music, scents, temperature, and cleanliness, which must be carefully monitored and controlled regularly. Studies confirm that pop-up store atmospherics should involve a range of sensory stimuli—including tactile, gustatory, olfactory, and visual elements—as well as social factors, location, space, and the target audience.

By making a simple comparison between a traditional store and a pop-up store, it becomes clear that the atmosphere of a pop-up store involves fewer variables than that

of traditional stores. Since pop-up stores are temporary by nature, retailers do not plan large budgets for them, nor do customers expect a luxurious shopping experience. Instead, pop-up stores emphasize modernity, innovation, and the momentary atmosphere that consumers enjoy the most. Nevertheless, careful planning and attention to detail in the internal environment remain crucial to ensuring the success of pop-up stores, as they are often a multichannel extension of the retailer. It represents a golden opportunity to expand the brand's reach to a new list of customers (Ibrahim & Chua, 2010).

According to the researcher, tourist behavior and the factors influencing it are complex and cannot be studied in isolation from external stimuli. These stimuli may act as triggers or motivators that facilitate the occurrence of the desired behavior in tourists, or they may be analyzed to accurately and objectively understand them. The researcher believes that in order to understand the factors influencing tourist consumer behavior, it is necessary to study all concepts related to this behavior. Consumer behavior reflects the motives and incentives that unfold through a sequence of steps comprising a set of activities that vary across time and place and are influenced by different roles, as well as both external and internal factors.

Study Methodology

The descriptive approach is considered one of the most important methodologies employed in scientific studies. It is employed to describe a specific phenomenon accurately, helping to understand the phenomenon under study, place it within its proper framework, and explain all the surrounding conditions. This contributes to reaching the results, recommendations, and suggestions that the study aims to identify (Creswell, 2009). Accordingly, the study employed the descriptive-analytical method, a systematic approach to analysis and scientific interpretation that enables the description of a specific phenomenon and provides an accurate representation of its variables. The objective is to identify the impact of shopping at pop-up fashion stores on tourist behavior in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.

The study will undertake several procedures, the most important of which include obtaining the necessary approvals to conduct the research, preparing the research tools by developing and validating the instrument following established scientific procedures. The study will then analyze the correlational and causal relationships between the independent and dependent variables to reach the required conclusions.

This study employs the descriptive-analytical method, a structured form of scientific analysis and interpretation, to describe a specific phenomenon and provide an accurate description of its variables, thereby identifying the impact of shopping at pop-up fashion stores on tourist behavior in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The procedures include obtaining the necessary approvals to implement the study, as well as preparing the research tools, which involve developing the study instrument and verifying its validity and reliability according to established scientific standards. The study also identifies the correlational and causal relationships between the independent and

dependent variables to reach the required conclusions and formulate necessary recommendations that contribute to enhancing the understanding of tourists' behavior toward pop-up fashion stores in Saudi Arabia.

3.2 Sample Selection

The sample in this study was carefully chosen based on several key factors to ensure representativeness and reliability of the results. Major tourist locations in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia were identified, along with the peak tourist seasons in major cities such as Riyadh and Jeddah, to ensure a diverse and comprehensive sample of tourists. A random sampling method was employed to select participants, and data were collected from visitors present at the specified tourist sites during the designated periods.

Tourists who showed interest in visiting pop-up fashion stores and were willing to participate in the study were selected. A voluntary sampling approach was adopted, relying on participants' willingness to participate without any coercion from the researchers. Invitations to participate were communicated through media outlets and targeted advertisements aimed at tourists in Saudi Arabia.

The sample size was determined based on available statistics of the number of tourist visitors to tourist sites during peak seasons in Riyadh and Jeddah. The final sample consisted of 304 tourists, and statistical analysis was applied to the selected sample to produce generalizable results for the target population.

The sample size was calculated accurately using available statistics on the number of tourists visiting these locations and during these seasons. The calculation took into account the acceptable margin of error and the required confidence level to ensure the sample sufficiently represented the target population. The sample included a diverse group of tourists of different nationalities, ages, and backgrounds to ensure representativeness and reliability.

The sample size was calculated using several statistical formulas, including:

$$N = \frac{PQ(Z)^2}{E^2}$$

Where:

- **N** = Sample size
- **P** = Proportion of the population to be studied. If unknown, the maximum value (50%) is used
- **Q** = Complementary proportion (1 – P)

- **Z** = Standard score (1.96 for 0.05 significance; 2.58 for 0.01 significance)
- **E** = Sampling error (0.05 or 0.01)

For Riyadh, a sample of approximately 300 tourists was selected, while in Jeddah, the sample was around 200 tourists. Data were analyzed using statistical software to ensure accurate results and to inform practical recommendations. The final sample size of **304 tourists** was determined after reviewing previous literature, similar studies, and consulting experts in the field to ensure sample representativeness and the validity of the results.

3.3 Study Instruments

The study instruments were developed based on the measurement scales used in previous research and consist of a questionnaire. The questionnaire was carefully designed and developed to cover the hypotheses on which the study is based, using evaluative statements to determine the significance of the responses provided by the sample. A five-point Likert scale was adopted to assess the relative importance of each item in the questionnaire.

The research instruments were reviewed and validated before data collection to ensure their reliability and validity. The questionnaire was designed to be easy for tourists to complete, with clear instructions provided to ensure a proper understanding of the questions. It included multiple-choice questions as well as open-ended questions to collect comprehensive and analytical information about tourist shopping behavior at pop-up fashion stores in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The questionnaire was administered to the selected sample after clarifying the purpose of the study and assuring participants of the confidentiality of their responses.

3.3.1 Instrument Construction

The study instrument was built based on the theoretical model and hypotheses of the study, which focus on key dimensions such as shopping enjoyment and positive emotions, as well as other factors including the store's internal environment, product novelty and uniqueness, and ephemerality. Accordingly, the instrument was designed as follows:

- Identifying items and questions: Based on the study hypotheses, a set of items and questions was developed to cover the main dimensions of the research. Questions were included to assess shopping enjoyment and positive emotions, evaluate the store environment, and assess product novelty and ephemerality.
- Five-point Likert scale: A five-point Likert scale was used to evaluate each item, ranging from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree." The scale was applied as follows:
 - (1) Strongly Disagree
 - (2) Disagree

- (3) Neutral
- (4) Agree
- (5) Strongly Agree

To interpret the arithmetic means of the respondents' ratings for each questionnaire item and each domain, the following Likert scale criterion was used (Table 2):

$$\text{Interval Length} = \frac{\text{Maximum} - \text{Minimum}}{\text{Number of Levels} - 1} = \frac{5 - 1}{3} = 1.33$$

Based on this, the levels were classified as follows:

- **1.00 – 2.33** → Low
- **2.34 – 3.67** → Moderate
- **3.68 – 5.00** → High

3.3.2 Validity and Reliability of the Measurement Tool

To evaluate the **validity and reliability** of the measurement tool, a series of essential steps and procedures were followed:

- **Content Review:** First, the content of the questions was examined to ensure alignment with the study objectives and the relevant literature.
- **Internal Consistency & Interpretive Ability:** The internal consistency and explanatory power of the tool were assessed using a pilot sample to evaluate question clarity and make necessary revisions before applying the instrument to the final sample.

To measure **validity**, several methods were employed:

- **Face validity:** Experts in the field reviewed the items to confirm that they appeared to measure the intended constructs.
- **Content validity:** A panel of experts examined the questionnaire content to ensure it adequately represented key concepts and aligned with the study objectives.
- **Construct validity:** A small pilot sample was used to assess participants' understanding of the questions and whether the items accurately captured the intended concepts.

To measure **reliability**, **Cronbach's alpha** was used to test internal consistency. The instrument was administered to a sample twice at appropriate time intervals to assess the stability of results over time. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient was calculated to ensure that the items measured the same concept in a consistent and uniform manner. After applying these procedures, the tool was confirmed to be both valid and reliable,

thereby increasing the credibility of the study's results and the accuracy of subsequent analyses.

3.4 Procedures for Administering the Study Instrument

To apply the study instrument regarding factors influencing tourist behavior in shopping at pop-up fashion stores in Saudi Arabia, the following steps were taken:

1. The questionnaire was carefully designed to cover factors related to tourist shopping behavior at pop-up fashion stores.
2. A sample of tourists who visited pop-up fashion stores in Saudi Arabia was selected to participate in the study.
3. Potential participants were contacted through appropriate communication channels and invited to participate.
4. The questionnaire was distributed to participants, along with clear instructions on how to complete it.
5. Data were collected from respondents either electronically or through paper forms, depending on their preference.
6. Statistical software such as SPSS was used to analyze the data and extract statistical results.
7. The validity of the instrument was evaluated by analyzing its content and ensuring alignment with the study objectives and relevant literature.
8. Cronbach's alpha was calculated to assess the reliability of the tool and confirm its ability to consistently measure the variables.
9. The final results were analyzed to identify the impact of various factors on tourist behavior when shopping at pop-up fashion stores in Saudi Arabia.
10. All procedures and steps followed during the implementation were documented to ensure the study's transparency and reliability.

Results and Discussion

4.2 Demographic Characteristics of the Study Sample

The study sample consists of a group of tourist visitors who were carefully selected from major tourist sites in Riyadh and Jeddah during the most active tourist seasons. This was done to ensure that the sample is representative and reliable. The total number of participants was **304**, which is sufficient to examine the demographic characteristics and analyze the distribution of the sample according to different variables such as gender. The details are as follows:

1. Gender

Frequencies and percentages were calculated for the demographic variable (**gender**), as shown in the table below:

Table 1. Distribution of the study sample according to the demographic variable (gender)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	120	39.5%
	Female	184	60.5%
Total		304	100%

Examining the table on gender distribution reveals that female participants comprise 60.5% of the sample (184 participants), while male participants account for 39.5% (120 participants). This disparity reflects a female predominance in the sample, which may be related to several factors, such as the nature of the visitors present at the tourist sites during the study period or possibly a greater willingness among women to participate in such studies.

Moreover, the sample was randomly selected from tourist sites during specific seasons, which enhances the credibility of the findings. This suggests that the demographic distribution shown in the table likely reflects the actual visitor profile during the targeted periods. However, the gender distribution is not balanced, which may affect the analysis of results later, especially when examining the relationship between gender and other variables.

This demographic distribution is also an important indicator for understanding the nature of visitors to tourist sites. For example, such data may help clarify the differences between men and women in terms of tourism behavior or service preferences. Therefore, it is crucial to consider this gender disparity during data analysis to ensure accurate and unbiased interpretation.

The figure illustrates the distribution of the study sample by gender, showing the percentage of male and female participants. The total number of participants was 304, divided into two main groups: male and female, providing a clear view of the sample's demographic composition. The gender imbalance may influence interpretation, particularly if gender is a significant factor in the variables being studied. Nevertheless, the random sampling approach from tourist sites during defined seasons strengthens the validity of the results and reflects the real visitor demographics.

This distribution underscores the importance of carefully analyzing results while considering gender-based differences in tourist behaviors and preferences. These data may help identify potential gender-based differences, primarily if the study aims to provide recommendations for improving tourism services or targeting specific visitor groups.

2. Age

Frequencies and percentages were calculated for the demographic variable (**age group**), as shown in the table below:

Table 2. Distribution of the study sample according to the demographic variable (age group)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age Group	18–24 years	36	11.8%
	25–34 years	55	18.1%
	35–44 years	58	19.1%
	45–54 years	61	20.1%
	55 years and above	94	30.9%
Total		304	100%

The table indicates that the 55 years and above age group represents the most significant proportion of participants, accounting for 30.9% (94 participants). The 45–54 years group follows this at 20.1% (61 participants). Together, these two older groups comprise almost half of the total sample, indicating strong participation from older age groups.

The 35–44 years age group represents 19.1% (58 participants), while the 25–34 years group accounts for 18.1% (55 participants). The 18–24 years group has the lowest representation at 11.8% (36 participants).

This distribution reflects diversity in participants' ages but also shows a clear dominance of older age groups. This may be linked to the nature of visitors at the tourist sites or to a greater tendency among older individuals to participate in such studies. The differences in representation across age groups may influence the analysis of results, particularly if age is a significant factor affecting other variables being studied.

It is therefore recommended to interpret the results while taking these age group differences into account to ensure accurate conclusions and provide a comprehensive picture of the study sample. These data may help identify age-related differences in tourism behaviors or preferences, supporting the achievement of the study objectives in more detail.

3. Educational Level

Frequencies and percentages were calculated for the demographic variable (**educational level**), as shown in the table below:

Table 3. Distribution of the study sample according to the demographic variable (educational level)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Educational Level	Bachelor's	186	61.2%
	Master's	41	13.5%
	Doctorate	21	6.9%
	Other	56	18.4%
Total		304	100%

The data indicate that most participants hold a Bachelor's degree, accounting for 61.2% (186 participants). Master's degree holders follow this at a rate of 13.5% (41 participants). Doctorate holders represent 6.9% (21 participants), indicating limited participation from this educational group compared to others.

In contrast, the category classified as "Other", which may include educational levels lower than a bachelor's degree or non-academic qualifications, represents 18.42% of the total sample, with 56 participants.

This distribution reflects a clear focus on participants with higher education levels (Bachelor's degree and above), which may be due to the nature of the locations where the data were collected or the target population of the study. When analyzing the results, it is important to consider this distribution, as educational level can significantly influence participants' understanding of and interaction with the studied topics.

Accordingly, these data can be used to understand potential differences in behaviors or opinions based on educational level, while ensuring careful interpretation of the results to avoid bias arising from the heavy representation of one particular group.

4. Income Level

Table 4. Distribution of the study sample according to the demographic variable (income level)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Income Level	Less than 3,000 SAR	63	20.7%

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
	3,000 – < 6,000 SAR	31	10.2%
	6,000 – < 9,000 SAR	46	15.1%
	9,000 – < 12,000 SAR	51	16.8%
	12,000 SAR and above	113	37.2%
Total		304	100%

The table shows the distribution of participants according to their monthly income level. The total sample consisted of 304 participants. The data reflect variations in income levels, offering deeper insights into the participants' economic characteristics.

The largest proportion of participants belongs to the high-income group (more than 12,000 SAR), representing 37.2% (113 participants). This indicates a strong representation of the high-income segment in the sample, which may suggest that the study is associated with a particular social segment.

Participants with an income between 9,000 and less than 12,000 SAR represent 16.8% (51 participants), followed by those earning 6,000 to less than 9,000 SAR, who represent 15.1% (46 participants). In contrast, the middle-income group (3,000 to less than 6,000 SAR) is the least represented, at 10.2% (31 participants). Participants earning less than 3,000 SAR make up 20.7% of the sample (63 participants).

This distribution indicates notable diversity in income levels among participants, with dominance of the high-income group. Such a distribution may influence the study's findings, as income is a significant factor affecting individuals' behaviors and preferences—particularly in studies related to shopping, tourism, or any topic involving purchasing power.

Therefore, it is recommended to consider income differences during the analysis to ensure accurate and balanced conclusions. This distribution can also be used to understand how economic status influences the results related to the study's subject.

5. Place of Residence

Table 5. Distribution of the study sample according to the demographic variable (place of residence)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Place of Residence	Saudi Arabia	297	97.7%
	Outside the Kingdom	7	2.3%
Total		304	100%

The table illustrates the distribution of participants based on their place of residence. Out of the total 304 participants, the overwhelming majority (97.7%, or 297

participants) reside in Saudi Arabia, while only 2.3% (7 participants) are from outside the Kingdom.

This distribution reflects the study's focus on residents within Saudi Arabia, which may relate to the nature or primary objectives of the research. The relatively small percentage of participants from outside the Kingdom may not be sufficient to represent a significant segment of visitors or individuals living abroad. Consequently, the findings are expected to be more representative of the local context.

From a statistical standpoint, this distribution is appropriate if the study primarily aims to examine trends or characteristics of individuals within Saudi Arabia. However, the limited number of international participants could be a limitation if the objective were to compare or understand differences between local and international populations.

Based on these findings, it can be concluded that the study largely reflects the views and preferences of residents in Saudi Arabia, thereby enhancing the reliability of the results in this context. Nonetheless, future research could benefit from increasing the representation of participants from outside the Kingdom to gain a more comprehensive perspective.

The item *"The size of the aisles inside the store makes it easy to access products smoothly"* obtained a mean of (3.12) with a standard deviation of (1.77), indicating that having sufficient space inside the store contributes to customer comfort during shopping, though it is not among the most influential factors compared to others.

The item *"The interior design of the store is flexible and adaptable to seasonal changes"* received a mean of (3.10), suggesting that a store layout that allows for seasonal adaptation may be an influential factor, but to a lesser degree than elements such as lighting and cleanliness.

Finally, the least influential factor was *"The impact of the nature of the displayed products on purchasing decisions in the store"*, with a mean of (3.04). This indicates that purchasing decisions are influenced more by the store environment and overall experience than by the nature of the products themselves.

Overall, the results presented in the table highlight the importance of the store's internal environment in enhancing the shopping experience. Good lighting, cleanliness, and the availability of product information play a key role in improving customer satisfaction and encouraging purchasing decisions. In contrast, the impact of other factors—such as aisle design and interior layout flexibility—was relatively lower. Based on these findings, it is recommended to focus on improving in-store lighting and cleanliness, as well as providing clear product information to enhance the shopping experience and increase purchase rates.

4.5 Discussion of the Study Results

The study's findings revealed that the multiple linear regression model was able to explain a large proportion of the variance in tourists' shopping behavior in pop-up fashion

stores in Saudi Arabia, with an adjusted coefficient of determination (R^2) of (0.863). This result confirms that the four examined factors—store environment, perishability, product novelty and uniqueness, and shopping enjoyment—are key determinants of consumer behavior. This aligns with Creswell (2009), who emphasized the importance of statistical models in explaining social and behavioral phenomena.

First: The Effect of the Store Environment

The results showed that the store environment had the greatest influence on tourists' shopping decisions, although it was not statistically significant at the (0.05) level. This finding is consistent with studies by Kotler (1973) and Turley & Milliman (2000), which indicated that store atmospherics (lighting, colors, music, ventilation) directly affect consumer satisfaction and willingness to purchase. Similarly, the findings support Jonas & Renaud (2015), who emphasized that the physical store environment enhances positive consumer emotions and increases purchase intentions. Locally, the Saudi Commission for Tourism and National Heritage (2018) indicated that improving the quality of exhibition and event environments enhances the attractiveness of the tourism experience.

Second: The Effect of Perishability

The results revealed that perishability ranked second in terms of impact. Consumers showed a greater tendency to purchase when they perceived product scarcity or limited availability. This aligns with the findings of Henkel & Toporowski (2021, 2022), who reported that the temporary nature of pop-up stores creates a “FOMO” (fear of missing out) effect, pushing consumers to make quick decisions. Boustani (2021) also argued that “ephemeral retail” relies on creating a sense of scarcity to attract consumers. This is further supported by the Saudi Ministry of Media (2022) during the “Outlet Festival,” which reported that limited-time offers contribute to increased purchasing demand.

Third: The Effect of Product Novelty and Uniqueness

The results indicated that product novelty and uniqueness had a clear impact on purchase decisions, as consumers seek unique and innovative designs. This finding is in line with Niehm et al. (2007) and Ryu (2011), who found that product innovativeness enhances customer loyalty and purchase intentions. Similarly, Alexander, Varley, and Nobbs (2018) highlighted the role of pop-up stores as platforms for testing new products and strengthening brand identity. Locally, Saudi Vision 2030 supports such innovations in the retail sector to enhance competitiveness.

Fourth: The Effect of Shopping Enjoyment

Finally, the results showed that shopping enjoyment had a relatively lower impact compared to the other factors. Nonetheless, it remains valuable in enhancing the overall customer experience. This finding aligns with Taube & Warnaby (2017), who noted that sensory and emotional engagement in pop-up stores strengthens brand image, though it may not be the primary purchase driver. Similarly, Thomas et al. (2018) observed that the “buzz” factor in pop-up stores enhances customer experience but does not replace the

importance of scarcity and novelty. This is also consistent with the Saudi General Entertainment Authority (2022), which emphasized the importance of creating enjoyable and innovative experiences for visitors during tourism events.

Conclusions and Recommendations

First: Conclusions

Based on the results of the statistical analysis and the field study, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Store Environment:

The findings revealed that the store environment (lighting, colors, cleanliness, and space design) is the most influential factor affecting tourists' shopping behavior. An attractive atmosphere and well-designed layout encourage consumers to stay longer in the store, thereby increasing the likelihood of making a purchase.

2. Perishability:

The temporary nature of fashion pop-up stores significantly enhances purchasing behavior. Time limitations and product scarcity create a sense of urgency (FOMO), motivating consumers to make quicker decisions.

3. Product Novelty and Uniqueness:

The results showed that products with exclusive and innovative designs increase the desire to purchase. Consumers are eager to acquire unique items that are not available in traditional markets, underscoring the importance of innovation in fostering customer loyalty.

4. Shopping Enjoyment:

Although shopping enjoyment ranked last in terms of impact, it remains a complementary element of the purchasing experience. Enjoyable shopping experiences enhance customer satisfaction and increase the likelihood of repeat visits.

Second: Recommendations

Based on the above conclusions, the study proposes the following practical recommendations:

- **Enhance the store environment** by improving lighting, selecting attractive colors, and providing comfortable interior spaces that make the shopping experience more enjoyable.
- **Focus on scarcity strategies**, such as limited-time offers and exclusive editions, to create a sense of urgency among consumers and boost sales.
- **Encourage innovation and uniqueness** in product design by offering exclusive collections that meet the needs of tourists seeking distinctive items.

- **Integrate entertainment elements** within pop-up stores, such as promotional events, live performances, or music, to make the shopping experience more interactive and appealing.

Third: Suggestions for Future Research

- Conduct comparative studies between pop-up and permanent stores to understand similarities and differences in consumer behavior.
- Examine the impact of cultural and social factors on shopping decisions in pop-up stores within Saudi Arabia.
- Expand research on **digital marketing** related to pop-up stores, such as the role of social media in increasing consumer engagement.
- Conduct quantitative and qualitative research to explore the experiences of **international tourists** compared to **domestic tourists** when visiting pop-up stores.

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